

The Rise of the Academic Science Humble Brag

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Academic science has always had a competition for jobs, for funding, and for career advancements. This creates pressures on scientists to get their work, and themselves, noticed. There is nothing new to that. However, competition has increased with an increase of PhDs and declining opportunities in academia [1]. The means of getting noticed have also changed in an interconnected world. And, most critically, the need to be noticed has been enhanced by changes in the way universities conduct business.

Universities promote themselves by advertising the accomplishments of their faculty, post-docs, and graduate students. They now have paid staff and writers to track and write public dissemination articles about awards, honors, papers published, and grants received. A goal of such institutional marketing is to maximize what might be termed academic profit: Rankings and external funding. As a result, faculty members regularly receive emails with subject lines like “It’s time to brag about yourself”. Self-promotion becomes not just a step to an academic career but is normalized as a requirement throughout an academic career – a part of playing the game if one wants to stay in the game.

Scientists, like all humans, have egos of variable intensities. Bragging and self-promotion comes easier for some. However, all scientists appreciate, or are at least aware, that science is a collective endeavour, and, giving our louder colleagues the benefit of the doubt, no one wants to sound like a complete ego-driven asshole to their colleagues. How to square the circle of feeling the need to brag, in order to maintain a career, while not wanting to sound like a braggard? That question has led many to throw in a touch of the humble and humble brags now permeate science and the internet.

Humble brags can start early in a scientist’s career:

- 1) I can’t believe I got a perfect GRE score and didn’t even study.
- 2) I am honored and humbled to be only one of two people selected for a prestigious post-doctoral fellowship that had over a thousand applicants.

One could argue this is in the effort to get into academics. However, humble brags tend to grow stronger once a job is secured:

- 3) I am so proud of our paper published in Nature with my graduate student co-author and contributions from undergraduates.
- 4) Wow, so happy to get my NSF grant funded given how many good proposals were submitted.
- 5) Cheers to my post-doc on being awarded best poster for our research on ...
- 6) Hats off to the editor of Science who saw the value of our research.
- 7) Congratulations to my co-authors for our paper being the most cited research from my department over the last month.
- 8) I can’t believe our research work was highlighted on NOVA and YouTube.
- 9) What would you do with 1.72 million dollars? We know what we will do as we just got the funding for some really interesting research on _____. It was such a group effort. Stay tuned for updates!

Interested readers can find many more examples. Once you realize what to look for, in terms of the humble science brag, you may be surprised by how easily you find it and you may even wonder why you didn't see it before in the very same places you had been looking at all along. An easy entry point is to find academic webpages that maintain a "News" section, with updated threads.

The entry point above is but one avenue and webpages have become passe for many in terms of getting noticed. The changing ways in which one can now get noticed, in a more and more interconnected world, has led to a meta-level form of humble bragging. Social media platforms allow for enhanced exposure. Many academic scientists will publicly decry social media, while realizing that if bragging is a career requirement it would be dangerous to not take advantage of the platforms. How to square that circle? It can be done and it leads to one of our favorite forms of the humble brag. It is meta and it is, in a dark way, masterful. It takes the form of:

- 10) I don't like social media but if I don't tweet about my scientific research then the true science about the subject will not get out to the public.

The humble brag may help spread information and, one could argue, knowledge. It is bragging as social service, in other words. That said, it is motivated to a larger degree by a garnering of attention. It was predicted, some time ago, that a drive for attention, in a digitally interconnected world, would redefine value within the world economy [2]. Academic science falls under that umbrella more so than it did in the past, especially given the rise of universities adopting business models. The rise of the humble brag may reflect science becoming one more entity vying for attention in an attention economy.

But all of this is harmless, is it not? What harm could come from upping the bragging a tad to help advertise? If one has doubts, just recall that 'it ain't bragging if it's true' (just because you nominate yourself for an award doesn't mean you don't deserve the award – someone even nominated themselves for a Nobel Peace Prize, so you can claim to be in lofty company).

Besides, there is no conflict between bragging and the higher goals academic scientists may have, is there? They can play an ever-increasing game of hyper-competition, to keep administrators happy, and at the same time argue that more healthy academic work place environments are needed to promote inclusivity within the sciences. The latter is noble while the former is harmless, is it not? Surely, hyper-competition has no effect on those higher goals and, even if it maybe does, one can tweet about the noble goals to offset a humble brag or two, or three, or ... Circles can be squared in many ways.

References

- [1] OECD (2021), "Reducing the precarity of academic research careers", *OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, No. 113*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/0f8bd468-en>.
- [2] Goldhaber, M.H. (1997), Attention Shoppers: The Currency of the New Economy Will Not Be Money, but Attention: A Radical Theory of Value, *Wired Magazine*.

Some Bonus Thoughts

This Op-Ed was run by a few colleagues. One of them, Jerome Ravetz (a philosopher), suggested an analogy and quickly hooked on to an issue of logic that sits between the lines of the piece.

The analogy is to Linus, the Peanuts' cartoon character. Linus believes in the great pumpkin, who only visits the most-sincere child on Halloween night. He is aware that he is not the only child who wants to be honored by the great pumpkins' visit. Linus accepts that he must show to the great pumpkin that he is indeed the most-sincere, with the most-sincere of pumpkin patches. Each year he sits up all night to show his sincerity. Each year he is disappointed but he accepts that he must keep at it. The years play out the same.

Figure 1. Only the most-sincere will be rewarded and you have to prove you are more sincere than the rest. There is nothing illogical about that, is there?

The logic issue is akin to classic paradoxes like “This Statement is False”. With humble bragging, we now have: The Claim That ‘I am Sincere’ is Made Sincerely. Opportunities for iteration, to an infinite recursive sequence, are easily seen.

Jerome noted an added connection related to the American adventure in Vietnam: "How can we lose when we're so sincere?" - Question haunting Richard Holbrooke. Review by Roger Boyes of 'Our Man' by George Packer, Times Saturday Review, 19/05/11.